

In the present work a film of Ag_2S was formed by long exposure of silver specimen in aqueous hydrogen sulphide solution in access to oxygen and light according to the following reaction

According to Barschevskii⁵ the photocurrent and the spectral characteristics ($i = f\lambda$) for AgBr and other silver halide varies with layer thickness. The cause of such variation is the changes in the relative number of surface light absorption centres at the surface and internal photoelectric effects such as acid volume centres (dissociating excitons).

Fig. 2.

According to the literature no visible image formation takes place in an Ag_2S film by the action of sunlight. Contrary to this it has been found in the present study that Ag_2S films formed by the action of H_2S water on silver are photosensitive and produce visible images without the application of a developer. Thus, upon exposure to sunlight an image was formed of the marking on the glass container through which the radiation was passed (Fig. 1). In another experiment the two surfaces of the treated plates were connected to a sensitive ballistic galvanometer and the current produced when one surface of the treated plate was exposed to sunlight was measured as a function of time. A typical graph obtained is displayed in Fig. 2. The most interesting feature of the curve is the reversal of polarity. Similar reversals of polarity have also been reported by Tamura et al⁶ who measured the photocurrent in compacted and sintered AgBr powder and found the forward currents to increase to a maximum and then to decrease to an equilibrium value.

The probable explanation is that Ag_2S which is formed in excess of photo-adsorbed oxygen is converted to Ag_2O and SO_2 according to the reaction

During this conversion the photocurrent increases and after a layer of Ag_2O film is formed on top of Ag_2S , the current levels off. The levelling of current may be due to the semiconducting layer of Ag_2S and Ag_2O . Ag_2S being an 'n' type semiconductor and Ag_2O 'p' type semiconductor; form a *pn* junction.

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Abnormal Products in a Condensation Reaction

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N-Hydroxymethylphthalimide has been reported to condense with primary aromatic amines yielding N-arylamino-methyl-phthalimides in good yields¹. This reaction was employed to prepare N-(2-chloro-4-nitroaniline) methylphthalimide (I) by treating 2-chloro-4-nitroaniline with N-hydroxymethylphthalimide. However this condensation reaction did not furnish the expected product (I). From the reaction mixture two substances were isolated: a white crystalline solid (A), soluble in ethanol, m.p. 229° and a yellow crystalline solid (B), insoluble in ethanol and sparingly soluble in glacial acetic acid, decomposing above 260°.

The infrared spectrum of A indicated presence of NH (3175 cm^{-1}) and C = O groups (1770 1750, cm^{-1}) and absence of nitro group and was identical with the infrared of phthalimide. Its mixed m.p. with phthalimide did not show any depression. The elemental analysis was in accordance with phthalimide. Therefore substance A appears to be phthalimide.

The infrared spectrum of B showed absorptions due to NH (3378 cm^{-1}) and nitro groups (1344, 1500 cm^{-1}) and was devoid of C = O absorption. The elemental data was in agreement with the proposed structure (II). Its extreme insolubility in

common organic solvents and its high m.p. prevented the recording of n.m.r. and mass spectra. On the basis of this limited data the structure of B appears to be II. II was also obtained when

phthalimide, formaldehyde and 2-chloro-4-nitroaniline were allowed to react in equimolar amounts. When 2-chloro-4-nitroaniline and formaldehyde were refluxed II was again obtained. The identity of the products isolated from these reactions was checked by comparing their i.r. spectra which were identical. The isolation of methylenebis amines (of secondary amines) have also been reported earlier²⁻⁴.

The formation of II from (a) N-hydroxymethylphthalimide and 2-chloro-4-nitroaniline, (b) phthalimide, formaldehyde and 2-chloro-4-nitroaniline and (c) 2-chloro-4-nitroaniline and formaldehyde is believed to take place by the following mechanism :

Experimental :

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are not corrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 Spectrophotometer in KBr.

Condensation of N-Hydroxymethylphthalimide with 2-Chloro-4-nitroaniline : N-Hydroxymethylphthalimide (1.77g.; 0.01 mole) was suspended in 20 ml of hot ethanol. To this suspension 1.72 g.(0.01 mole) of 2-chloro-4-nitroaniline was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 min. During this period a yellow amorphous mass deposited in the flask. The contents of the flask were cooled and filtered. The solid mass was boiled in ethanol and filtered hot. The filtrate on cooling yielded a white crystalline solid (A) which was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. and mixed m.p. with phthalimide 229°; i.r. : 3175 cm⁻¹ (NH), 1770, 1750 cm⁻¹ (C = O); the i.r. spectrum was identical with phthalimide. (Found : N, 9.49 per cent. Calcd. for C₈H₅NO₂ : N, 9.52 per cent)

The yellow residue (B) was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. > 260°d. i.r. : 3378 cm⁻¹ (NH), 1344, 1500 cm⁻¹(NO₂). (Found : C, 43.85; H, 3.18; N, 15.17 per cent. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₀Cl₂N₄O₄ : C, 43.71; H, 2.82; N, 15.69 per cent).

Condensation of phthalimide with 2-chloro-4-nitroaniline and formaldehyde in equimolar proportions gave identical results.

Methylenebis (2-chloro-4-nitroaniline) (II)

A mixture of 2-chloro-4-nitroaniline (1.72 g.; 0.01 mole) and 2 ml of 37% formalin in 20 ml of ethanol was refluxed for 30 min. At the end of this period the contents of the flask were cooled and filtered. The yellow solid product thus obtained was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. > 260°, i.r.

3378 cm⁻¹ (NH), 1344, 1500 cm⁻¹ (NO₂). The i.r. spectrum was identical with the product B obtained above. (Found : C, 44.15; H, 3.34; N, 15.10 per cent Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₀Cl₂N₄O₄ : C, 43.71; H, 2.82; N, 15.69 per cent)

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Coordination Complexes of Paludrine with Ferrous Sulphate and Cobalt Chloride

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IN continuation of our work^{1,2} on the metal complexes of antimalarials, herein we describe iron and cobalt complexes of paludrine. The object in view is to see if these complexes may serve a double purpose of being antimalarial and at the same time antianaemic.

Experimental :

Paludrine recrystallised m.p. 129° (lit. 130°), ferrous sulphate E.P. and cobalt chloride A.R.

Conductivity measurements :

Conductivity measurements of (i) Ferrous sulphate-Paludrine in 80% methanol and (ii) Cobalt chloride-Paludrine in 80% ethanol were carried out at 20° using 'Toshniwal' conductivity bridge and dip type electrodes. 10 ml. of the ligand was diluted to 200 ml. and titrated against the metal solution. After the volume corrections, the results are plotted in Fig. 1, which indicate 2:1 complex formation.

mole) in the same solvent containing 2 drops of sulphuric acid to stabilize the divalent iron. Base

Fig. 1. Metal salt = 0.01 M : Ligand = 0.005 M ; t = 20°.

solution was added slowly to the ferrous sulphate solution with constant stirring. At first no change was observed but after some time the solution became turbid more and more. On cooling in an ice bath for several hours, a brick red complex separated, which was filtered, washed with methyl alcohol and dried in vacuum; yield 1.0 g, m.p. 200°.

(b) Paludrine base 1.5 g (2 mole) and cobalt chloride 0.7 g. (1 mole) were dissolved separately in minimum quantities of absolute alcohol. Paludrine solution was added slowly to the cobalt chloride solution and cooled in an ice bath for 4 hrs. The colour of the solution changed from dark blue to reddish brown and no complex separated. It was refluxed for 3 hrs on water bath with water condenser. The reddish brown colloidal solution changed to blue. It was cooled and the excess of solvent evaporated on water bath. The complex was filtered, washed with ether and dried; yield 1.1 gms., m.p. 280° d.

Analysis :

Iron was estimated by cupferron³ as oxide. Cobalt was estimated as tetrapyridine-cobalt-dithionate⁴ after removing the base and nitrogen by modified

TABLE I

Composition of the complex	percentages	Fe/Co	SO ₄ /Cl	N	H ₂ O
(C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₅ Cl) ₂ .FeSO ₄ .2H ₂ O	Found	7.82	13.14	19.14	5.40
	Requires	8.03	13.82	20.14	5.18
(C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₅ Cl) ₂ .CoCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	Found	8.24	9.70	20.20	4.72
	Requires	8.76	10.54	20.81	5.34

Isolation :

(a) Paludrine base 1.5 g. (2 mole) was dissolved in methyl alcohol while ferrous sulphate 0.8 g. (1

Kjeldahl's method⁵. Chloride, sulphate and water were estimated by usual methods.

The analytical results for paludrine-ferrous sulphate and paludrine-cobalt chloride complexes are given in Table I.

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